

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SUPERVISORY AND ORGANIZATIONAL
SUPPORT AND PROFESSIONAL QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG
FILIPINO GUIDANCE ASSOCIATES AND DESIGNATES:
TOWARDS A SUPPORTIVE SUPERVISION
PROGRAM FRAMEWORK**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 6

Pages: 654-667

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2995

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14814763

Manuscript Accepted: 01-06-2025

Relationship Between Supervisory and Organizational Support and Professional Quality of Life among Filipino Guidance Associates and Designates: Towards a Supportive Supervision Program Framework

Paul John Gojar,* Francis Michael P. Yambao, Erna V. Yabut

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The lack of Registered counselors in the Philippines urged schools to hire Non-RGCs called Guidance Counselor Associates (GCAs) and Guidance Designates (GDs) to take on the role and work with students' concern. This study examines how supervision quality and organizational support influence the professional quality of life (ProQoL) of GCAs and GDs in the Philippines. Data were gathered from thirty five (n=35) non-registered school counselors supervised by Registered Guidance Counselors (RGCs) using the Survey form containing demographic profile, Supervisor Support Scale (SSS), Perceived Organizational Support Scale (POS) and Professional Quality of Life Scale (ProQOL). Counselors reported average ProQoL levels, with lighter caseloads improving compassion satisfaction (CS) and reducing burnout (BO) and secondary traumatic stress (STS), while heavier caseloads increased stress. Both genders reported neutral supervision, with public and private school counselors agreeing on moderate supervisory support. Neutral organizational support (POS) highlighted the need for improved practices, such as better education assistance and salary increases. Public institutions faced greater emotional challenges, while elementary counselors reported the highest CS, and those handling multiple levels experienced the lowest CS and highest BO. Though SS and POS were not found significant predictors of ProQoL, a strong correlation was found between these two supports. The study underscores the need for supportive supervision and organizational policies, proposing a supervision framework to enhance counselor well-being.

Keywords: *supervisor support, organizational support, guidance counselors, guidance designates, professional quality of life*

Introduction

The practice of school counseling supervision plays a vital role in developing skilled and effective practitioners (ACA, 2014; PGCA, 2021). It involves guiding counselors to refine their professional skills, cultivate their professional identities, and enhance their beliefs and attitudes for the benefit of their clients (PGCA Code of Ethics, 2009). Counseling supervisors carry the dual responsibility of overseeing counseling services and ensuring client welfare while fostering the professional growth of counselors (ACA, 2014).

In the Philippines, school counseling supervision is primarily administrative rather than clinical, with site supervisors focusing on standards-based approaches and professional development (Dizon & Chavez, 2022). Supervision within master's programs typically occurs in group settings during practicum or internship experiences, where students are responsible for securing their own practice sites. These sites often provide varying levels of supervision, supplemented by peer mentoring (Tuason, Alvarez, & Stanton, 2021). As a result, Filipino counselors experience autonomy differently from their Western counterparts. While Western models emphasize a gradual transition to independent practice, Filipino counselors often work autonomously from the start due to limited formal supervised training. Thus, autonomy in the Philippines is shaped by the local training environment rather than a structured progression (Mateo & Salanga, 2012).

The Philippines is facing a critical shortage of licensed and qualified school counselors, with only 1,096 out of 4,474 registered members of the Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association (PGCA) actively working in primary and secondary schools (Harrison, King, & Hocson, 2023). This shortage is compounded by high entry requirements, limited career advancement opportunities, and lower salaries compared to other education professionals. As a result, many schools have increasingly relied on guidance associates or designates to take on roles traditionally filled by Registered Guidance Counselors (RGCs). Given this situation, it is crucial to explore the level of support counselors receive from their supervisors and the school. It was apparent that strong organizational and supervisory support can improve job satisfaction, foster professional growth, and help retain counselors, especially as many schools depend on less-qualified staff. This support is essential for ensuring that counselors can provide effective services to students, despite the challenges they face. This need for support is further highlighted in existing literature and studies.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between supervisory and organizational support and the components of professional quality of life among Guidance Counselor Associates (GCAs) and Guidance Designates (GDs) in the Philippines. Additionally, the study aims to inform the development of a framework for a supportive supervision program based on the quantitative findings. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the professional quality of life (levels of compassion satisfaction, burnout, and secondary traumatic stress), the quality

of Supervisory and Organizational Support perceived by Guidance associates and Designates in the Philippines based the following demographic factors:

- 1.1. sex;
- 1.2. number of students;
- 1.3. student level (e.g., elementary, secondary, tertiary); and
- 1.4. work setting (private vs. public institutions)?
2. What type of support do Guidance associates and designates receive from their supervisors and the organizational environment?
3. Is there a significant relationship between supervisor support and the components of professional quality of life (compassion satisfaction, burnout, and secondary traumatic stress) among Guidance associates and designates?
4. Is there a significant relationship between organizational support and the components of professional quality of life (compassion satisfaction, burnout, and secondary traumatic stress) among Guidance associates and designates?
5. Do organizational and supervisory support levels predict the Professional Quality of Life (ProQol) variables, such as Compassion Satisfaction, Burnout, and Secondary Traumatic Stress, based on the number of variance?
6. How can the findings from this study inform the design of a supervision program framework for Non-license Counselors?

Literature Review

Supervising Guidance Counselor Associates and Designates

Supervision is a purposeful, interpersonal process in which experienced counselors guide less experienced ones, helping them develop the necessary skills, knowledge, and ethical standards for their roles (Bernard & Goodyear, 2019). The American Counseling Association (2022) underscores that supervisors play a key role in assisting counselors in navigating complex educational environments, building cultural competence, and integrating leadership and advocacy into their practices. However, the shortage of counselors affects the availability and quality of supervisors. Some schools and universities run counseling programs without board-certified counselors overseeing them. In such cases, advocates and designates—often without formal qualifications—handle counseling cases under the guidance of licensed counselors serving in administrative roles. Despite heavy caseloads and unclear role definitions, they remain committed, viewing their work as a vocation rather than just a job (Decena & Singson, 2022). However, as new counselors, supervision is even more critical, as they often lack the experience to manage the challenges they will encounter. Dizon and Chavez (2022) highlight that limited resources and inconsistent supervision practices in the Philippines further underscore the need for improved training for supervisors and a more systematic, holistic approach to supporting counselors throughout every stage of their professional development.

The Philippine Guidance Counselor Association (2021) in its code of Ethics underscores the supervisor's role in helping counselors acquire professional competencies and improve their practices to ensure client welfare. Calma (2008) notes that supervision, particularly at the postgraduate level, provides an opportunity for reflection and alignment between counselors' growth and supervisors' expertise. Bohecker (2019) also stresses the importance of continuous supervision for building a well-rounded skill set, improving counseling outcomes, and sustaining professional growth. New counselors, in particular, need consistent, structured guidance to develop foundational skills and avoid ethical concerns and burnout.

The contrast between Western and local supervision models highlights the gap in formal training for counselors in the Philippines. In Western systems, supervision is an ongoing and integral part of both education and professional practice, with a strong focus on developing autonomy and professional growth (ASPB, 2009). However, the Philippine Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004 (Republic Act No. 9258) does not mandate a supervised internship for counselors seeking licensure, leading to significant variability in supervision practices. As a result, some counselors, even those still completing graduate studies or lacking formal training, may assume counseling roles as Guidance Associates or Designates. In these cases, supervision focuses primarily on administrative tasks such as implementing services, performance evaluations, and compliance with mandated protocols, rather than on clinical supervision (Nicasio, 2019). Peer supervision is common in the Philippines (Mendoza, 2021), but it lacks the structure and formal guidance necessary for new counselors.

In light of these challenges, there is an urgent need to establish a more structured and supportive supervision framework for Filipino guidance associates and advocates who are often new to the profession. Addressing the gaps in training, supervision practices, and the overall environment will not only improve counselors' professional development but also enhance counseling outcomes and ensure better support for both counselors and clients.

Professional Quality of Life (ProQol)

The Professional Quality of Life (ProQOL), as defined by Stamm (2010), is a measure of the emotional impact experienced by individuals in helping professions. It focuses on both the positive and negative aspects of a counselor's work experience. ProQOL includes compassion satisfaction, which refers to the joy and fulfillment derived from helping others, as well as compassion fatigue, which encompasses burnout and secondary traumatic stress resulting from prolonged exposure to clients' trauma. This phenomenon is not only evident among licensed counselors but also among pre-licensed counselors working directly with clients in a school setting

without complete qualifications. Recent studies have shown that the professional quality of life of pre-licensed counselors is strongly linked to the negative personal effects of affective distress, with the most significant impact observed between burnout and depression (Fye et al., 2021). This suggests that pre-licensed counselors experiencing burnout are also likely to experience depression. Furthermore, novice professional counselors often describe their burnout as an emotional experience resulting from challenging work conditions, such as low wages and long hours, as well as the use of negative coping strategies to deal with emotional distress when faced with challenging client issues (Cook et al., 2021). Counselor Burnout Inventory (CBI) proposed by S. M. Lee et al. (2007) provides a wider view of counselors' experience of burnout as explained in their five-dimensional model unique to their experience which scale includes Exhaustion, Incompetence, Negative Work Environment, Devaluing Client, and Deterioration in Personal Life. These factors on burnout are considered in the study.

In a study conducted by Garcia (2018), it was discovered that counseling paraprofessionals actively participate in self-care practices to enhance their overall well-being, ultimately leading to a more positive professional quality of life. The research indicated that these individuals reported moderate levels of job satisfaction, as well as low instances of burnout and secondary traumatic stress. The impact of self-care behaviors on these outcomes varied among participants. Furthermore, Bonganciso & Bonganciso (2022) emphasized the significance of demographic factors in influencing compassion satisfaction among professionals in the field. Their research revealed that counselors working in school settings tend to experience higher levels of satisfaction, particularly based on age and subject specialization. Interestingly, no significant differences were observed based on gender, age, area of specialization, or years of service. This suggests the need for further investigation in the current study to better understand these findings.

Life satisfaction was considered a key predictor of the positive workplace outcomes of Filipino counselors as found in the study of Mateo & Salanga (2018). It suggested that life satisfaction positively predicts flow state and emotional awareness in counselors, aligning with the broaden-and-build theory's assertion that positive affect enhances psychological resources. Successful counseling therefore is more dependent on the counselor's personal qualities than on specific techniques. Counselor's personal qualities play a more significant role in successful counseling than the specific techniques they use. One of these is their emotional intelligence (EI) that was proven to influence the professional quality of life of counselors in addition to their confidence in working with clients, and self-criticism. Higher EI is linked to greater job satisfaction and less burnout, highlighting its importance for counselors (Pankratova and Nikolaeva, 2022).

Wellness has consistently been linked to improved professional quality of life in the field of counseling. Lawson and Myers (2011) highlighted that higher counselor wellness is associated with better career-sustaining behaviors and reduced burnout, advocating for the integration of wellness models into counselor training. Similarly, Dang & Sangganjanavanich (2015) recognized the risk of impairment among counselors due to their work and the need to prioritize wellness through self-care, peer collaboration, and systemic advocacy. They proposed a multi-level approach, offering strategies at individual, group, and policy levels to improve counselor well-being and enhance counseling effectiveness at work. Existing models of counseling supervision that integrates wellness exists in the face of Wellness Model of Supervision (WELMS), which emphasizes the use of wellness checks and personalized wellness plans to help counselors-in-training (CITs) reflect on their experiences and adopt self-care strategies, ultimately fostering greater work satisfaction through practices like loving-kindness and self-compassion. These studies provide a foundational framework for the current research, which aims to explore the role of wellness in supervision and counselor development (Callender and Lenz, 2018).

Supervisor and Organizational Support

Supervisor and organizational support are crucial factors in promoting the mental health, job satisfaction, and overall effectiveness of counselors, particularly for non-licensed professionals such as Guidance Counseling Associates (GCAs) and Guidance Designates (GDs) in school settings. Research consistently emphasizes the positive impact of supervisory support on reducing workplace stress, preventing burnout, and enhancing job satisfaction (Hammer et al., 2024; Said & Muzakki, 2024). This is especially pertinent in schools, where the emotional well-being of students is a priority. Support from licensed guidance counselors plays a key role in ensuring the competence and effectiveness of non-licensed counselors, helping them navigate their responsibilities and challenges.

Prosocial behaviors such as empathy, warmth, and respect are closely linked to enhanced job satisfaction and reduced stress among counselors. McCarthy and McCarthy (2023) argue that positive interpersonal relationships—both with peers and supervisors—are essential for counselors' well-being. Their study highlights the buffering effect of prosocial behaviors, demonstrating that the combination of support from both supervisors and peers can compensate for each other, reinforcing the importance of a holistic support system. Similarly, Cole et al. (2023) found that Caribbean guidance counselors who felt adequately prepared for their roles experienced stronger professional and social support. This finding suggests that preparedness, training, and support systems are critical components of counselor satisfaction and effectiveness, regardless of the school setting or geographic location. These studies underline the importance of fostering supportive supervisor-supervisee relationships, particularly for non-licensed counselors who may face unique challenges due to their role status. Effective supervision not only enhances counselor performance but also contributes to their emotional and professional growth.

In addition to supervisor support, organizational backing plays a significant role in shaping school counselors' job satisfaction and effectiveness. Strong support from school administration—through clear role definitions, adequate resources, and empowerment—can greatly enhance counselors' engagement and performance (Liu & Huang, 2024). Organizational support helps meet counselors'

psychological needs, contributing to their sense of fulfillment and increasing their capacity to provide high-quality mental health services to students. Liu and Huang (2024) stress that clear empowerment from administrators enables counselors to navigate complex school environments, such as addressing disparities in school discipline, which can hinder counselors' effectiveness without adequate administrative backing (Administrators Leveraging School Counseling Supports to Address Disparities in School Discipline, 2022).

However, the challenges that counselors face in school settings—such as resource limitations, unclear role expectations, and organizational constraints—can significantly hinder their ability to perform their duties effectively. Ghukasyan (2022) points out that these challenges, particularly during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic, highlight the vulnerability of counseling programs to systemic issues. To mitigate these barriers, Crandall et al. (2020) suggest that decision-support systems be implemented to aid counselors in making data-driven decisions despite resource limitations. By providing counselors with the necessary tools, guidance, and resources, school administrations can help alleviate these constraints, enhancing counselors' ability to support students' mental health effectively. Fye et al. (2021) further emphasize the critical role of ongoing organizational support in maintaining counselors' well-being and providing effective client care. Supportive work environments that prioritize counselor self-care, professional development, and manageable workloads are vital for sustaining the well-being of counselors and, by extension, their students.

The well-being of counselors has emerged as a central theme in the literature on supervision and organizational support, with many studies highlighting the importance of self-care practices for both counselors and their supervisors. Professional associations, such as the Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association (2021) and the American Counseling Association (2019), stress that self-care is essential for promoting counselors' mental health and job satisfaction. Supervisors and organizations must create supportive work environments that encourage self-care and provide adequate resources to help counselors manage their emotional and professional demands. Gallardo and Chavez (2022) argue that work environments that foster positive interpersonal relationships, psychological safety, and professional growth are critical in enhancing job satisfaction and mitigating burnout. Research also points to the value of supervision, consultation, networking, and collaboration with administrators, particularly principals, as essential components of a supportive work environment (Holman, Nelson, & Watts, 2019; Harrison, King, & Hocson, 2023). These factors contribute to the development of effective counseling programs and help counselors address the professional challenges they encounter. However, the connection between counselor support systems and their compassion satisfaction remains underexplored, presenting an opportunity for future research.

Despite the wealth of research on supervisor and organizational support, there is a noticeable lack of studies focusing on non-licensed counselors, such as GCAs and GDs, especially in the Philippines, despite giving items on this to many schools in both public and private educational institutions. These groups play a vital role in the delivery of counseling services in Philippine schools. The absence of local studies addressing the specific supervision practices and support systems for these professionals underscores a gap in the literature that this study seeks to fill. By examining the quality of support provided by supervisors and organizations to non-licensed counselors, the study aims to shed light on the unique challenges faced by GCAs and GDs, particularly those who are new to the field and often at the forefront of school counseling efforts. The findings from this research will provide a foundation for developing a supportive supervision framework that can guide the creation of effective training programs and educational initiatives for school counselors. Ultimately, the goal is to enhance professional growth, reduce burnout, and foster healthier work environments, thereby improving both counselor well-being and student outcomes in school counseling settings.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a Quantitative-correlational research design to investigate the relationship between supervisory and organizational support and the components of professional quality of life (compassion satisfaction, burnout, and secondary traumatic stress) among Guidance Counselor Associates (GCAs) and Guidance Designates (GDs) in the Philippines. A quantitative approach was appropriate for this study as it allowed for the systematic measurement of variables and the use of statistical techniques to identify patterns and relationships among them (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). The correlational aspect of the design was particularly suitable for examining associations without manipulating variables, ensuring the findings reflected real-world dynamics in natural work settings (Salkind, 2010). By analyzing these relationships, the study addressed complex interdependencies between demographic factors, supervisory and organizational support, and professional quality of life, enabling the development of evidence-based recommendations for a supportive supervision framework.

Respondents

The study focused on guidance associates and advocates working in educational institutions and community organizations across the Philippines. Due to the limited number of counselors supervised by registered professionals in Philippine educational institutions, only 35 counselors ($n=35$) participated in the correlational study, which meets the minimum requirement of 30 respondents necessary for accurate correlation analysis, as outlined by Fraenkel and Wallen (2009). These participants were selected through convenience sampling to ensure diversity in terms of experience, education, and organizational backgrounds. Participants were eligible in the criteria set by the researcher which includes the following: Filipino citizens, non-licensed counselors employed full-time as guidance associates or designates, hold a Master's degree in Guidance and Counseling or a related field (or be currently pursuing it), have at least one year

of experience in their current role, be actively working at the time of the study, and provide informed consent acknowledging their understanding of the study's purpose, risks, benefits, and rights.

Table 1. The demographics of Guidance Counselor Advocates and Designates are presented through frequency and percentage distribution tables

Demographics		
	n	%
Sex		
Male	7	20.0
Female	28	80.0
Setting		
Public Educational Institution	15	42.9
Private Educational Institution	20	57.1
No. of Handled Students		
< 250	1	2.9
251-500	8	22.9
501-750	6	17.1
751-1000	9	25.7
> 1000	11	31.4
Level of Handled Students		
Elementary	1	2.9
Secondary	7	20.0
Tertiary/ College	16	45.7
Elementary and Secondary	6	17.1
Secondary and Tertiary	2	5.7
All Levels	3	8.6

Instrument

The study utilized three validated instruments—the Supervisory Support Scale (SSS), the Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS), and the Professional Quality of Life Scale (ProQOL)—to examine key factors influencing the well-being and professional experiences of Philippine guidance counselor associates and designates. The SSS, developed by Greenhaus, Parasuraman, and Wormley (1990), assesses perceived career support from supervisors through nine items on a 5-point scale. With a Cronbach's alpha of 0.93 and established correlations with career satisfaction and performance, the SSS is particularly relevant in understanding how supervisory relationships impact the professional development of guidance counselors in the Philippine educational and counseling sectors. The Perceived Organizational Scale (POS) developed by Eisenberger, et. al (1986), has 9 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale, evaluates employees' perceptions of organizational support, including care for their well-being and professional growth. With a Cronbach's alpha of 0.97 and demonstrated validity through its relationship with absenteeism and commitment, this scale is highly applicable in exploring how Philippine organizations foster environments conducive to the success and retention of counseling professionals.

The ProQOL, tailored for caregiving professionals, examines compassion satisfaction (CS), burnout (BO), and secondary traumatic stress (STS), offering critical insights into the well-being of counselors exposed to the emotional demands of their roles. Using normative data from Stamm (2010) and localized insights from Hegarty and Buchanan (2021), the ProQOL allows for nuanced analysis of professional quality of life in the Philippine context, where cultural, institutional, and systemic factors may shape counselors' experiences uniquely. The data collected using these instruments will help illuminate the challenges and supports specific to Philippine guidance counselor associates and designates, enabling stakeholders to implement targeted interventions that enhance their professional satisfaction and mitigate burnout. By applying these validated tools in this setting, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of the interplay between supervisory, organizational, and professional quality of life factors in shaping the effectiveness and well-being of non-licensed school counselors in the Philippines.

Procedure

Data collection for this study occurred in two phases: recruiting participants and administering the survey. Participants were recruited through professional networks, social media, and outreach to educational and advocacy organizations to ensure a diverse sample. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before the study began, with detailed information provided about the study's purpose, procedures, and risks.

Surveys were administered online using Google Forms, chosen for its ease of use and confidentiality. Participants had two weeks to complete the survey, with reminder emails sent during this time to encourage participation. After the data collection period, responses were exported for analysis, which included descriptive statistics for demographics and inferential statistics to examine relationships between supports and professional quality of life. This approach ensured the study's findings were reliable and valuable.

Data Analysis

Data analysis focused on examining relationships between supervisory and organizational support and the components of professional quality of life (compassion satisfaction, burnout, and secondary traumatic stress) among Guidance Counselor Associates (GCAs) and Guidance Designates (GDs) in the Philippines. Using the SPSS version 28 for Mac was used to calculate the descriptive statistics employed to demographic profiles, including sex, client levels, years of experience, and work settings. Specifically, measure of variability and central tendency was utilized to explore the levels of professional quality of life, supervisory and organizational support, while Pearson's correlation assessed the relationship between SS, POS and the components of the ProQol. Multiple regression analysis further evaluated the combined predictive effects of SS and POS on Variables of professional quality of life, revealing their significance in explaining variance in compassion satisfaction, burnout, and secondary traumatic stress.

The findings were aligned with existing frameworks and studies, emphasizing the connection between support systems and counselor well-being. Each hypothesis was tested, and the results were discussed in detail. These insights served as the basis for designing a supervision program framework to strengthen support for GCAs and GDs in the Philippines.

Ethical Considerations

The study took several steps to ensure ethical standards were met, prioritizing participant well-being and research integrity. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they understood the study's purpose, risks, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequences. Participant confidentiality was maintained by removing personal identifiers and securely storing data. The study underwent the process of review and validations of results. These measures upheld ethical standards and respected participants' rights.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings of the study and explains their meaning in relation to the research questions. It explores how supervisory and organizational support relate to the professional quality of life of Guidance Counselor Associates (GCAs) and Guidance Designates (GDs) in the Philippines. The results are compared with existing research, highlighting their practical implications and how they can inform the creation of a supportive supervision program.

Sex and the Professional Quality of Life, Supervisor and Organizational Support

Table 2. Sex and the Professional Quality of Life, Supervisor and Organizational Support

	Male			Female			Total		
	M	VI	SD	M	VI	SD	M	VI	SD
Compassion Satisfaction (CS)	38.1	Moderate	6.07	37.7	Moderate	3.50	37.8	Moderate	4.03
Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS)	27.6	Moderate	11.12	22.0	Moderate	8.18	23.1	Moderate	8.95
Burnout (BO)	23.3	Moderate	4.68	20.7	Low	6.16	21.2	Low	5.93
POS MEAN	3.143	Neutral	.7232	3.406	Neutral	.4598	3.354	Neutral	.5211
SSS MEAN	4.033	Agree	.8479	4.381	Agree	.6640	4.312	Agree	.7050

The data in Table 2 examines the professional well-being of guidance counselors, focusing on compassion satisfaction (CS), burnout, secondary traumatic stress (STS), perceived organizational support (POS), and supervisor support (SSS) among male and female counselors.

Both male and female counselors report moderate levels of compassion satisfaction (CS), with males slightly higher at 38.1 and females at 37.7, suggesting they experience some emotional rewards from their work. For burnout, both genders report low levels, with males at 23.3 and females at 20.7, indicating a generally healthy work environment. However, females show more variability in burnout scores, suggesting that some experience higher levels of burnout. Regarding secondary traumatic stress (STS), both genders report moderate levels, with males at 27.6 and females at 22.0, but with higher variability among males, suggesting some may be more affected by trauma. As for perceived organizational support (POS), both groups report neutral levels of support, with males at 3.14 and females at 3.41, indicating there is room for improvement in organizational resources. In contrast, both groups report strong satisfaction with supervisor support (SSS), with males at 4.03 and females at 4.38, suggesting that good supervisory support is key to managing stress and improving well-being. Overall, the data shows that while counselors experience moderate levels of satisfaction and stress, strong supervisor support plays an important role in their professional satisfaction, while organizational support could be improved (Bonganciso & Bonganciso, 2022; Maslach & Leiter, 2016).

Settings and the Professional Quality of Life, Supervisor and Organizational Support

Table 3 shows that guidance counselors in public and private institutions report low levels of Compassion Satisfaction (CS), with slightly higher satisfaction in private institutions ($M = 38.0$). CS variability is greater in public institutions ($SD = 5.05$), indicating

diverse emotional experiences. Burnout (BO) levels are also low, with more variability among public counselors (SD = 7.23), suggesting higher burnout risks in these settings. Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS) is low across both groups but more variable in public institutions (SD = 11.61), reflecting greater exposure to trauma-related challenges. These findings align with Bonganciso & Bonganciso (2022), who noted varying emotional rewards for school counselors.

Table 3. *Settings and the Professional Quality of Life, Supervisor and Organizational Support*

	Public Educational Institution			Private Educational Institution			Total		
	M	VI	SD	M	VI	SD	M	VI	SD
Compassion Satisfaction (CS)	37.5	Moderate	5.05	38.0	Moderate	3.19	37.8	Moderate	4.03
Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS)	24.8	Moderate	11.61	21.8	Low	6.32	23.1	Moderate	8.95
Burnout (BO)	21.7	Low	7.23	20.8	Low	4.89	21.2	Low	5.93
POS	3.458	Neutral	.5503	3.275	Neutral	.4977	3.354	Neutral	.5211
SSS	4.267	Agree	.6507	4.345	Agree	.7580	4.312	Agree	.7050

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is neutral in both settings (M = 3.458 for public, M = 3.275 for private), indicating room for improvement in organizational practices to reduce stress and enhance support. In contrast, Supervisor Support Scale (SSS) scores are high in both groups (M = 4.267 for public, M = 4.345 for private), highlighting the protective role of supervisory relationships in reducing stress and promoting well-being, consistent with Maslach et al. (2001).

Number of Students handled, Professional Quality of Life, Supervisory and Organizational Support

Table 4. *Number of Students handled, Professional Quality of Life, Supervisory and Organizational Support*

Number of Clients Handled		Compassion Satisfaction (CS)	Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS)	Burnout (BO)	POS	SSS
< 250	M	42.00	16.00	16.00	3.0000	5.0000
	VI	Moderate	Low	Low	Neutral	Strongly Agree
	SD
251-500	M	37.88	21.88	20.38	3.6250	4.5688
	VI	Moderate	Low	Low	Agree	Strongly Agree
	SD	3.182	6.937	5.397	.32733	.60236
501-750	M	36.67	21.67	22.17	3.2708	4.4450
	VI	Moderate	Low	Low	Agree	Agree
	SD	3.777	6.186	5.811	.38256	.68234
751-1000	M	36.89	26.78	22.67	3.2083	4.0756
	VI	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Agree	Agree
	SD	3.822	10.305	7.246	.55199	.73993
> 1000	M	38.64	22.36	20.55	3.3523	4.1827
	VI	Moderate	Low	Low	Neutral	Agree
	SD	5.025	10.698	5.820	.66101	.76518
Total	M	37.77	23.09	21.20	3.3536	4.3117
	VI	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Neutral	Agree
	SD	4.030	8.952	5.925	.52114	.70496

The data in Table 4 demonstrates the impact of caseload size on the Professional Quality of Life (ProQol) of guidance counselors. Counselors with lighter caseloads (fewer than 250 students) report the highest compassion satisfaction (CS)(M = 42.00), the lowest secondary traumatic stress (STS) (M = 16.00), and the lowest burnout (BO) (M = 16.00). These results suggest that counselors handling fewer students are able to experience more emotional rewards from their work, with minimal emotional exhaustion or trauma exposure. However, as caseloads increase, particularly for those handling 751-1000 students, CS drops (M = 36.89), and both STS (M = 26.78) and burnout (M = 22.67) increase. This indicates that larger caseloads are associated with reduced job satisfaction and heightened stress, which is consistent with literature that links workload to emotional exhaustion and trauma (Stamm, 2010).

Perceived organizational support (POS) remains neutral across all groups, with the highest score reported by counselors managing 251-500 students (M = 3.625), while those with larger caseloads report slightly lower levels of POS. Supervisor support (SSS) is strongly endorsed by all groups, though it slightly decreases as the number of students increases, from M = 5.00 for those handling fewer than 250 students to M = 4.0756 for those managing 751-1000 students. These findings underscore the significant role of organizational and supervisory support in protecting counselors from the negative effects of high workloads. Enhancing these supports, particularly for those handling larger caseloads, could help reduce burnout and secondary trauma, thus improving counselors' overall well-being (Cole et al., 2023; Liu & Huang, 2024).

Number of Students handled and the Professional Quality of Life, Supervisor and Organizational Support

Table 5 highlights variations in the Professional Quality of Life (ProQol) among guidance counselors based on the educational levels they handle. Elementary counselors report the highest compassion satisfaction (CS) (M = 40.0), while those handling both elementary and secondary levels report the lowest (M = 35.3), likely due to increased demands. Burnout (BO) is highest among elementary

counselors (M = 23.0) and those managing both levels (M = 22.8), indicating greater emotional exhaustion in these roles. Secondary counselors report the highest secondary traumatic stress (STS) (M = 25.9), reflecting challenges in working with older students. Perceived organizational support (POS) is neutral overall, with the highest score for counselors handling all levels (M = 3.79) and the lowest for those managing elementary and secondary levels (M = 3.06).

Table 5. Number of Students handled and the Professional Quality of Life, Supervisor and Organizational Support

Level Handled		Compassion Satisfaction (CS)	Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS)	Burnout (BO)	POS	SSS
Elementary	M	40.0	22.0	23.0	3.500	3.670
	VI	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Agree	Agree
	SD
Secondary	M	40.7	25.9	20.4	3.429	4.397
	VI	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Neutral	Agree
	SD	3.59	11.88	6.43	.7212	.6781
Tertiary/ College	M	36.9	23.3	21.3	3.344	4.188
	VI	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Neutral	Agree
	SD	4.57	9.99	6.51	.4507	.7776
Elementary and Secondary	M	35.3	21.7	22.8	3.063	4.242
	VI	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Neutral	Agree
	SD	2.16	5.50	6.52	.5850	.7325
Secondary and Tertiary	M	40.0	21.0	20.5	3.313	4.610
	VI	Moderate	Low	Low	Neutral	Strongly Agree
	SD	2.83	7.07	6.36	.4419	.5515
All Levels	M	38.0	20.0	19.0	3.792	4.927
	VI	Moderate	Low	Low	Agree	Strongly Agree
	SD	2.00	6.08	3.00	.0722	.1270
Total	M	37.8	23.1	21.2	3.354	4.312
	VI	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Neutral	Agree
	SD	4.03	8.95	5.93	.5211	.7050

Supervisor support (SSS) is consistently high, peaking among counselors handling all levels (M = 4.93) and lowest for those at the tertiary level (M = 4.19). These findings emphasize the need for stronger organizational and supervisory support, especially for counselors working with multiple levels or secondary students, to reduce burnout and STS and improve well-being (Stamm, 2010).

Types of Support received

Supervisory Support received. The Table 6 Summarizes through frequency and percentage the different types of supervisory support received by respondents

Table 6. Supervisory Support received

Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Regular feedback on performance (e.g., performance reviews, constructive criticism)	20	57.14%
Collaboration opportunities (e.g., teamwork with colleagues on projects)	24	68.57%
Availability for support and guidance (e.g., approachable and accessible for questions)	28	80.00%
Guidance on professional development (e.g., support for career advancement)	23	65.71%
Recognition of counseling efforts (e.g., acknowledgment of impact and contributions)	19	54.29%

The data reflects the supervisory support received by respondents in various areas. The highest level of support was availability for support and guidance, with 80% of respondents feeling that supervisors are approachable and accessible when they need help. This points out the importance of supervisory relationships for counselors which should be built on trust and open communication, allowing counselors to express vulnerabilities and seek guidance (Gomersall, 2009). For GCAs and GDs, supervisors are seen as a valuable source of assistance. Collaboration opportunities also emerged as a significant support mechanism, with 68.57% of respondents mentioning the importance of collaborating as one team or organization. This indicates that supervisors facilitate a collaborative work environment, similar to group supervision that fosters collaborative learning through positive feedback and shared experiences among counselors enhancing their professional skills (Perrello, 2013).

Support related to professional development guidance was also prominent, with 65.71% of respondents indicating that their supervisors provide career advancement support. This suggests that supervisors are proactive in helping employees develop their skills and progress

in their careers. Regular feedback on performance, while important, was mentioned by 57.14% of respondents, suggesting that feedback may not be as frequent or consistent as other forms of support.

Finally, recognition of counseling efforts was mentioned by 54.29%, indicating that while recognition is valued, it may not be as regularly provided as other forms of supervisory support. The findings support the conclusions of the existing systematic review on supervision, which suggests that field supervision can have a positive impact on supervisees' skills, self-awareness, and self-efficacy (Lohani & Sharma, 2022).

Therefore, the data highlights that respondents highly value supervisory support in the areas of guidance, collaboration, and professional development. However, there is potential to enhance feedback and recognition practices to improve overall supervisory support.

Organizational Support received. The table 7 on the other hand, presents the organizational support received by Guidance Counselor associates (GCAs) and Guidance Designates (GDs) based on their responses. The data presented below gathered in the survey highlighted the types of organizational support received by Graduate Assistants (GAs) and Graduate Divisions (GDs).

Table 7. Organizational Support received

Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Professional development opportunities (e.g., workshops, training sessions)	27	77.14%
Access to resources for counseling (e.g., materials, tools and facilities)	25	71.43%
Clear communication from administration (e.g., regular updates, policies)	19	54.29%
Recognition for contributions (e.g., acknowledgment of efforts and achievements)	18	51.43%
Access to support services (e.g., mental health resources for students)	16	45.71%
Education assistance	10	28.57%
Salary or compensation increase	8	22.86%

The most common support was Professional Development Opportunities (e.g., workshops and training), with 77.14% of respondents (27 out of 35) citing it. This suggests that GAs and GDs value opportunities to grow professionally. Affirming that, providing them with autonomy and opportunities for professional development significantly enhances their job satisfaction and engagement (Liu & Huang, 2024). Access to Resources for Counseling, including materials and tools, was reported by 71.43% of participants (25 out of 35), showing a strong need for these resources.

Clear Communication from Administration, such as regular updates and policies, was mentioned by 54.29% (19 out of 35) of respondents, indicating that communication is an important form of support. Similarly, Recognition for Contributions (acknowledgment of efforts) was identified by 51.43% (18 out of 35), suggesting that recognition of work is appreciated. This indicates that supportive supervision is linked to enhanced subordinate performance and commitment, emphasizing the crucial role of supervisor involvement in providing organizational support (Frear et al., 2018).

Access to Support Services (like mental health resources) was noted by 45.71% (16 out of 35), while Education Assistance was mentioned by 28.57% (10 out of 35), indicating that educational support is less common. Salary or Compensation Increases were the least mentioned, with only 22.86% (8 out of 35) referring to it as a form of support. The findings imply that GCAs and GDs prioritize professional development and resources as key supports, with clear communication and recognition also important for job satisfaction and engagement. Lower emphasis on education assistance and salary increases suggests that growth opportunities and acknowledgment of efforts are more crucial than financial or educational support. Organizations should focus on these areas to enhance satisfaction and commitment.

Supervisory Support Correlation to Professional Quality of Life Variables

Table 8 reveals key relationships among the variables. Compassion Satisfaction (CS) is significantly negatively correlated with Burnout (BO) ($r = -0.44, p = 0.01$), indicating that higher compassion satisfaction is linked to lower burnout. However, CS shows no significant correlations with Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS) ($r = -0.20, p = 0.24$), Supervisory Support Scale (SSS) ($r = 0.02, p = 0.93$), or Perceived Organizational Support (POS) ($r = -0.03, p = 0.85$). Burnout (BO) is strongly positively correlated with STS ($r = 0.77, p < 0.001$), signifying that increased burnout is closely associated with higher secondary traumatic stress.

Weak negative correlations are observed between BO and SSS ($r = -0.30, p = 0.07$) and POS ($r = -0.24, p = 0.16$), though neither is statistically significant. Similarly, STS is weakly negatively correlated with both SSS ($r = -0.20, p = 0.25$) and POS ($r = -0.25, p = 0.14$), but these relationships are not significant. Lastly, SSS and POS are strongly positively correlated ($r = 0.66, p < 0.001$), suggesting that higher supervisory support aligns with greater organizational support, a statistically significant relationship.

Table 8. Supervisory Support Correlation to Professional Quality of Life Variables

Variables	M	SD	Compassion Satisfaction (CS)		Burnout (BO)		Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS)		Supervisory Support Scale (SSS)		Perceived Organizational Support (POS)	
			r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p
Compassion Satisfaction (CS)	37.77	4.03	1		-.44	.01	-.20	.24	.02	.93	-.03	.85
Burnout (BO)	21.20	5.93	-.44	.01	1		.77	.00	-.30	.07	-.24	.16
Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS)	23.09	8.95	-.20	.24	.77	.00	1		-.20	.25	-.25	.14
Supervisory Support Scale (SSS)	38.80	6.34	.02	.93	-.30	.07	-.20	.25	1		.66	.00
Perceived Organizational Support (POS)	26.83	4.16	-.03	.85	-.24	.16	-.25	.14	.66	.00	1	

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed)

Multiple Regression Analysis of POS, SS and Compassion Fatigue (CS)

The data on table 9 reveals that neither Supervisory Support Scale (SSS) nor Perceived Organizational Support (POS) significantly predict Compassion Satisfaction (CS) among guidance counselors. While SSS shows a positive but negligible relationship with CS (B = 0.041, Beta = 0.064, p = 0.785), and POS shows a weak negative association (B = -0.072, Beta = -0.074, p = 0.753), both are statistically insignificant. The significant constant (B = 38.116, p < .001) indicates that other unexamined factors likely influence compassion satisfaction. These results suggest that neither supervisory nor organizational support alone are key determinants of counselors’ compassion satisfaction, highlighting the need to investigate additional factors impacting their professional quality of life.

Table 9. Multiple Regression Analysis of POS, SS and Compassion Fatigue (CS)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Compassion Satisfaction (CS)	38.116	4.961		7.683	<.001
Supervisory Support Scale (SSS)	.041	.149	.064	.275	.785
Perceived Organizational Support (POS)	-.072	.226	-.074	-.318	.753

Multiple Regression Analysis of POS, SS and Burnout (BO)

The results show on table 10 that SSS has a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with burnout (B = -0.240, Beta = -0.257, p = .257), suggesting that higher supervisory support might slightly reduce burnout levels, though this effect is not statistically meaningful. Similarly, POS also shows a weak and insignificant negative relationship with burnout (B = -0.103, Beta = -0.072, p = .748), indicating that perceived organizational support has minimal influence on reducing burnout.

Table 10. Multiple Regression Analysis of POS, SS and Burnout (BO)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Burnout (BO)	33.288	6.947		4.792	<.001
Supervisory Support Scale (SSS)	-.240	.208	-.257	-1.154	.257
Perceived Organizational Support (POS)	-.103	.317	-.072	-.324	.748

However, the constant (B = 33.288, p < .001) is highly significant, suggesting that factors outside the scope of this model substantially influence burnout among counselors. These findings imply that while supervisory and organizational support may have some theoretical impact, they are not strong or direct predictors of burnout in this context. To effectively address burnout, future research should investigate additional factors such as workload, emotional stress, coping mechanisms, or institutional policies, which might offer a more holistic understanding and targeted strategies for mitigating burnout among counselors.

Multiple Regression Analysis of POS, SS and Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS)

Table 11. Multiple Regression Analysis of POS, SS and Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Secondary traumatic Stress (STS)	38.667	10.668		3.625	<.001
Supervisory Support Scale (SSS)	-.082	.320	-.058	-.258	.798
Perceived Organizational Support (POS)	-.462	.487	-.215	-.949	.350

The analysis presented on Table 10 shows that neither SSS nor POS significantly predicts STS. The constant term indicates a baseline level of STS (M = 38.667), which is statistically significant (p < 0.001). While SSS has a negative unstandardized coefficient (-0.082), suggesting a slight inverse relationship with STS, the relationship is not statistically significant (p = 0.798). Similarly, POS also shows a negative unstandardized coefficient (-0.462), indicating a potential reduction in STS with higher perceived organizational support, but this relationship is also not statistically significant (p = 0.350). Thus, these findings suggest that, despite the negative direction of

the relationships, neither SSS nor POS significantly influence STS levels in this sample.

The current study investigates how the elements of professional quality of life—burnout, secondary traumatic stress, and compassion satisfaction—are related to the supervisory and organizational support received by Guidance Counselor Associates (GCAs) and Guidance Designates (GDs). It outlines the variations in this data based on demographic factors such as gender, student grade level, job setting (public versus private), and student caseload. The study also examines whether the levels of supervisory support (SS) and perceived organizational support (POS) significantly correlate with or forecast professional quality of life outcomes, alongside the types of support that employees obtain from their supervisors and organizational structures. The primary objective of the research is to develop a framework for an effective supervision program for unlicensed counselors, leveraging insights from its quantitative findings to enhance their effectiveness and well-being.

The GCAs and GDs surveyed from both public and private institutions report low levels of Compassion Satisfaction (CS), with slightly better satisfaction outcomes in private settings. Public institutions display greater variability in CS, burnout (BO), and Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS), indicating increased emotional difficulties and elevated burnout risks. Perceived Organizational Support (POS) remains neutral across both environments, underscoring the necessity for improved organizational backing since a supportive framework and healthy workplace are crucial for counselors' satisfaction (Gallardo & Chavez, 2022). Supervisor Support (SSS) is reported as high in both categories, highlighting its importance in alleviating stress and enhancing counselor well-being. Gender does not show a significant impact on ProQoL outcomes (Kagan, 2023), yet the data reveals that both male and female counselors report moderate levels of compassion satisfaction (CS) and secondary traumatic stress (STS), with males showing slightly higher averages in both and greater variability in STS. Burnout rates are low for both sexes, and while supervisory support (SSS) is robust across the board, perceived organizational support (POS) is neutral, pointing to the need for improved resources to boost counselor well-being (Bonganciso & Bonganciso, 2022). Concerning student caseloads, lighter caseloads notably improve the professional quality of life for guidance counselors, correlating with higher compassion satisfaction and reduced burnout and secondary traumatic stress, while heavier caseloads result in diminished satisfaction and heightened stress (Browning et al.), underscoring the importance of stronger organizational and supervisory support to address workload-related challenges. Additionally, those working with elementary students report the highest levels of compassion satisfaction, whereas counselors handling both elementary and secondary grades experience the lowest satisfaction and highest burnout, indicating the pressure from increased demands. Secondary counselors encounter the highest levels of secondary traumatic stress. The sample exhibited average levels of POS and SS, indicating the necessity for enhanced support to tackle the emotional challenges faced while working across different educational levels.

When it comes to obtaining supervisory and organizational support, counselors indicate high levels of supervisor availability and guidance, with many perceiving their supervisors as approachable. There is considerable appreciation for collaborative opportunities and professional development; however, regular feedback and recognition are less commonly highlighted, signaling areas for improvement, as previous studies demonstrate that consistent communication and constructive feedback positively influence counselors' performance and confidence (Adedokun & Oyetunde-Joshua, 2024). Regarding organizational support, professional development and access to counseling resources are highly valued, alongside clear communication and recognition. Nonetheless, support services and salary increases receive less emphasis, indicating a need for improved feedback and compensation practices due to their effect on counselors' emotional experiences in their work (Cook et al., 2021). The connection between supervisory support and perceived organizational support with professional quality of life reveals that increased Compassion Satisfaction is related to lower levels of burnout, suggesting that satisfaction may serve as a protective factor against burnout (Asgharipour et al., 2023). However, CS does not show a significant relationship with Secondary Traumatic Stress, supervisory support, or organizational support, indicating that other variables might affect these aspects of well-being. Burnout is closely associated with STS, suggesting that individuals who experience more burnout are also more prone to face secondary traumatic stress (Stamm, 2010). The weak correlations between burnout and both supervisory and organizational support indicate that these influences have a limited effect on burnout. Similarly, STS exhibits weak connections with supervisory and organizational support, amidst existing research suggesting that a supportive framework and healthy workplace are critical elements in promoting counselors' satisfaction (Gallardo & Chavez, 2022). Nonetheless, a strong correlation exists between supervisory support and organizational support.

Conclusions

This study emphasizes a variety of paths for future research. This is among the few studies that investigate Non-licensed school counselors in the Philippines under the supervision of Licensed counselors thus, future studies could explore other areas related to this to further enrich the knowledge on the experiences of this special group. Although it offers important perspectives on the connection between professional quality of life (ProQoL)—including burnout, secondary traumatic stress, and compassion satisfaction—and supervisory/organizational support, its results emphasize the necessity for more research into unmeasured elements impacting the well-being of Guidance counselors associates and designates. Future research might investigate how caseload size, coping methods, and institutional policies influence ProQoL results, especially in environments with different degrees of perceived organizational support (POS) and supervisor support (SSS). Qualitative methods might be utilized to grasp counselors' intricate experiences, providing a richer insight into how demographic factors like gender, work setting, and student grade influence their professional quality of life. Furthermore, longitudinal research would be beneficial for comprehending the causal relationships and the lasting impacts of supervisory and organizational support on the well-being of counselors.

Furthermore, future research may examine the relationship between external elements—like economic circumstances, community issues, and availability of professional development resources—and ProQoL results. Exploring the impact of customized supervision methods on distinct counselor requirements, as indicated by Wanyama and Eyamu (2021), may further improve the efficiency of support frameworks. Ultimately, due to the weak predictive links between supervisory and organizational support and ProQoL outcomes found in this study, future investigations should explore other possible factors, such as workload management and mental health interventions. These initiatives may result in the creation of thorough, evidence-supported frameworks aimed at improving the effectiveness and welfare of counselors across various educational and organizational environments.

References

- Adedokun T.A & Oyetunde-Joshua F.. (2024). 4. Strengthening Student-Supervisor Relationships: An Examination of Postgraduate Students' Perspectives on Supervisory Supports. *JMSP (Jurnal Manajemen dan Supervisi Pendidikan)*, doi: 10.17977/um025v8i22024p95
- ACES Best Practices in Clinical Supervision 2011. (2018, November 28). ACES Online. https://acesonline.net/?attachment_id=239
- American Counseling Association. (2014). 2014 ACA code of ethics. <https://www.counseling.org/docs/default-source/default-document-library/ethics/2014-aca-code-of-ethics.pdf>
- Ashley, J., Blount., Abby, L., Bjornsen., Daniel, B., Kissinger., Kara, L., Schneider., Lindsay, M., Vik., Jessica, Gonzalez-Voller. (2022). 4. Wellness and Professional Quality of Life in Counselor-in-Training Interns: Assessment of Wellness and Non-Wellness-Infused Supervision. *Journal of wellness*, doi: 10.55504/2578-9333.1065
- Asgharipour N. et al. (2023). Investigating the Quality of Professional life of Mashhad Psychotherapists in 2022. *Iranian Journal of Psychiatry and Clinical Psychology*, 28(4):496-507. doi: 10.32598/ijpcp.28.4.4129.2
- Bohecker, L. (2019). Supervision as a Counseling Tool Kit. 439-452. doi: 10.4324/9781351164207-29
- Bonganciso, Jade & Bonganciso, Ruel. (2022). Compassion Fatigue and Satisfaction: A Professional Quality of Life (ProQoL) of Filipino Guidance Designates. *Journal of Education Society and Behavioural Science*. 35. 20-39. 10.9734/JESBS/2022/v35i830446
- Browning B.R , McDermott R.C , Scaffa M.E. (2019). Transcendent Characteristics as Predictors of Counselor Professional Quality of Life. *Journal of mental health counseling*, 41(1):51-64. doi: 10.17744/MEHC.41.1.05
- Choi, Y. (2021). Professional quality of life and affective distress among prelicensed counselors. *Ewha*. https://www.academia.edu/54134772/Professional_Quality_of_Life_and_Affective_Distress_Among_Prelicensed_Counselors
- Cole, S., McCarthy-Curvin, A., Thompson, C., Knight, V., Ferguson, T. , & Montgomery, A. (2023). Investigating guidance counselors' perceived sense of preparedness and support in carrying out their job. *Global Journal of Guidance and Counseling in Schools: Current Perspectives*, 13(2), 65–80. <https://doi.org/10.18844/gjgc.v13i2.9094>
- Cook, R. M., Fye, H. J., Jones, J., & Baltrinic, E. R. (2021). Self-Reported Symptoms of Burnout in Novice Professional Counselors: A content analysis. *The Professional Counselor*, 11(1), 31–45. <https://doi.org/10.15241/rmc.11.1.31>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (6th ed.). SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Dang, Y., & Sangganjanavanich, V. F. (2015). Promoting Counselor Professional and Personal Well-Being through Advocacy. *Journal of Counselor Leadership and Advocacy*, 2(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2326716x.2015.1007179>
- Decena , A. B. & Singson, D. E. (2022). Lights and Shadows: Lived Experiences of Guidance Advocates in the Practice of Ethical Bracketing. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 3(8).
- Dizon, M. A. A. D., & Chavez, M. L. L. (2022). Circumstances to Contribution: A Phenomenological Study on School Counseling Site Supervision in the Philippines. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 5(2), 105-117. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v5i2.497>
- Duffy, J. T., & Guiffrida, D. A. (2014). The heroic supervisor: Using the hero's journey to facilitate development in supervisors-in-training. *The Clinical Supervisor*, 33(2), 144–162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07325223.2014.978587>
- Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchinson, S., & Sowa, D. (1986). Perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71, 500-507. Items were taken from Table 1, p. 502. American Psychological Association.
- Estacio, R. D. (2019). The factors of compassion fatigue among guidance counsellors. *Global Journal of Guidance and Counseling in Schools: Current Perspectives*, 9(3), 115–130. <https://doi.org/10.18844/gjgc.v9i3.4343>
- Fraenkel, J.R & Wallen, N.E (2009). *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education* (7th ed). New York. McGraw-hill
- Fye, H.J., Cook, R.M., Choi, Y., & Baltrinic, E.R. (2021). Professional Quality of Life and Affective Distress Among Prelicensed

Counselors. *Journal of Counseling & Development*.

Gallardo, Maria & Chavez, Maria. (2022). Exploring the Well-Being of Guidance Counselors in the Philippines: A Phenomenological Study. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 5, 36-48. 10.52006/main.v5i1.475.

Garcia, J. S. (2018). Career Sustaining Behaviors and Professional Quality of Life among Filipino Counseling Paraprofessionals. *Philippine Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 20(1).

Gomersall J.D (2009). Training and supervision of counsellors. *Journal of The British Institute of Mental Handicap (apex)*, 12(3):98-99. doi: 10.1111/J.1468-3156.1984.TB00224

Gravetter, F. J., & Wallnau, L. B. (2009). *Statistics for The Behavioral Sciences*. Cengage Learning. DOI: 10.1007/s11628-009-002

Harrison, M. G., King, R. B., & Hocson, S. M. G. (2023). The roles of school counsellors in the Philippines: challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Psychologists and Counsellors in Schools*, 33(2), 161–174. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jgc.2023.4>

Hassell, K. D., & Dobbins, A. S. (2005). The Supervisor Support Scale: A Measure of Supervisor Support in the Workplace. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 10(1), 73–87. DOI: 10.1037/1076-8998.10.1.73

Hee, K. J., & Hee, H. J. (2020). The Effect of counselor's supervision experience on counselor development: Moderating effect of supervision satisfaction. *Journal of the Korea Academia-Industrial Cooperation Society*, 21(5), 281–293. <https://doi.org/10.5762/kais.2020.21.5.281>

Hegarty, D., Buchanan, B. (2021, November 29). Psychologist Norms for the Professional Quality of Life Scale (ProQOL). *NovoPsych*

Holman, L. F., Nelson, J., & Watts, R. (2019). Organizational variables contributing to school counselor burnout: an opportunity for leadership, advocacy, collaboration, and systemic change. *The Professional Counselor*, 9(2), 126–141. <https://doi.org/10.15241/lfh.9.2.126>

Joel O., et al. (2023). 2. Bolstering the Moderating Effect of Supervisory Innovative Support on Organisational Learning and Employees' Engagement. *Administrative Sciences*, doi: 10.3390/admsci13030081

Kagan M. (2023). The Role of Demographics, Professional Quality of Life and Public Image in Social Workers' Self-Esteem. *British Journal of Social Work*, doi: 10.1093/bjsw/bcad169

Karisse, A., Callender., Karisse, A., Callender., A., Stephen, Lenz. (2018). 8. Implications for Wellness-Based Supervision and Professional Quality of Life. *Journal of Counseling and Development*, doi: 10.1002/JCAD.12225

Lawson G., & Myers J. . (2011). Wellness, Professional Quality of Life, and Career-Sustaining Behaviors: What Keeps Us Well?. *Journal of Counseling and Development*, 89(2):163-171. doi: 10.1002/J.1556-6678.2011.TB00074.X

Lohani G., & Sharma P. (2022). Effect of clinical supervision on self-awareness and self-efficacy of psychotherapists and counselors: A systematic review.. *Psychological Services*, doi: 10.1037/ser0000693

Lee, J., Lim, N., Yang, E., & Lee, S. M. (2011). Antecedents and consequences of three dimensions of burnout in psychotherapists: A meta-analysis. *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, 42(3), 252–258. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0023319>

Maslach, C., Schaufeli, W. B., & Leiter, M. P. (2001). Job burnout. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52(1), 397–422. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.52.1.397>

Mateo, N. & Salanga, M. C. (2012). Autonomy in the Development and Practice of the Filipino Counselor. *Philippine Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 14(1) Retrieved last September 24, 2024, Retrieved from: <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=6811#:~:text=Findings%20from%20the%20current%20study%20on>

Mateo, N. J., & Salanga, M. G. (2018). Life satisfaction predicts positive workplace outcomes among Filipino guidance counselors. *Philippine Journal of Psychology*, 51(1). <https://doi.org/10.31710/pjp/0051.01.05>

Meydan, B., & Sağkal, A. S. (2023). Unraveling the Direct and Indirect Effects of Supervisory Working Alliance on Supervisory Satisfaction: The Mediating Role of Supervisee Disclosure in Supervision. *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*, 10(2), 291–300. <https://doi.org/10.52380/ijpes.2023.10.2.869>

McCarthy, A. K., & McCarthy, R. J. (2023). Job Satisfaction and Receiving Prosocial Workplace Behaviors Among Rehabilitation Counselors. *Rehabilitation Counselors and Educators Journal*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.52017/001c.74451>

Mendoza, S. A. (2021). Peers with benefits: Exploring peer supervision in the Philippine setting. Retrieved from https://animorepository.dlsu.edu.ph/etdd_counseling/3

Nicasio, M. (2019). Context and conceptualization of supervision in school counseling practicum. <https://>

animorepository.dlsu.edu.ph/etd_doctoral/520

Pankratova A.A, M.E., Nikolaeva. (2022). 5. Relationships between Emotional Intelligence, Professional Effectiveness, and Professional Quality of Life in Novice Counseling Psychologists. doi: 10.17759/psyedu.2022140302

Perrello, C.S (2013). Supportive Alignments & Teams in Group Supervision for School Counselors-in-Training.

Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association (PGCA) (2021), PGCA CODE OF ETHICS : Free download, Borrow, and streaming : Internet Archive. (2023, March 6). Internet Archive. <https://archive.org/details/pgca-code-of-ethics>

Rahmi A., Neviyarni, Suhaili., Riska, Ahmad. (2024). 1. Urgency of management and supervision guidance and counseling in an effort to create responsive and quality services. Indonesian Journal of Counseling and Development, doi: 10.32939/ijcd.v6i1.2752

Rita, B. (2020). 1. Supervision for School Career Counsellors: Supervisors' Opinion. doi: 10.22616/REEP.2020.045

Salkind, N. J. (2010) Encyclopedia of Research Design. SAGE Publications Inc. <https://us.sagepub.com/en-us/nam/encyclopedia-of-research-design/book232149>

Stamm, B.H. (2010). The Professional Quality of Life Scale: Compassion Satisfaction, Burnout, and Secondary Traumatic Stress (ProQOL). 2nd Edition. ProQOL.org.

Stamm, B.H. (2012). Helping the Helpers: Compassion Satisfaction and Compassion Fatigue in Self-Care, Management, and Policy. In A.D. Kirkwood & B.H. Stamm, Resources for Community Suicide Prevention. [CD]. Meridian and Pocatello, ID: Idaho State University. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/266284945_Helping_the_Helpers_Helping_the_Helpers_Compassion_Satisfacti on_and_Compassion_Fatigue_in_Self-Care_Management_and_Policy_of_Suicide_Prevention_Hotlines

Tuason, M. T. G., Alvarez, M. H., & Stanton, B. (2021). The counseling profession in the Philippines. Australian Counselling Research Journal, ISSN1832-1135, Vol. 15, Pages 20-25 retrieved from: <https://www.acrjournal.com.au/resources/assets/journals/Volume-15-SW-Issue-2021/Manuscript4%20-%20The%20Counselling%20Profession%20in%20the%20Philippines.pdf>

Wallace, K. M. (2021). Male counselors' experiences of their child-clients' trauma. International Journal on Social and Education Sciences (IJonSES), 3(4), 618-635. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijonSES.233>

Zeligman M. (2017). 2. Supervising Counselors-in-Training Through a Developmental, Narrative Model. Journal of Creativity in Mental Health, doi: 10.1080/15401383.2016.1189370

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Paul John Gojar

Angeles University Foundation – Philippines

Francis Michael P. Yambao, PhD

Centro Escolar University – Philippines

Erna V. Yabut, PhD

Centro Escolar University – Philippines